

The Bastiat paradox, a loss in stock market and compensation between stock market and options market

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April 27, 2023

Abstract

Frédéric Bastiat a well known economist and a polemist had given his approach of how destruction in an ideal economy is used for thriving another industry, the example of the broken window in "*Ce qu'on voit et ce qu'on voit pas*" is a testimony for how destruction can be an argument for creating employment for whatever reasons: my inspiration is this treatie for which i had been thinking about stock crashes and how a loss in stock market can be compensated in the derivatives market: We perform pricings of Asian and Vanilla options under our model, afterward we could use the fact that a crash in stock market is augmenting the labour market to understand that depressions are not always synonym of unemployment.

We propose a new probability space under which the labour market augment due to a stock crash because of some new kind of investors that believe in market power to recover after a depression or a crash that hit the market, what matters in this study is this kind of paradox between depressions and employment.

JEL Classification. G13, J01.

Key words and phrases. Fractional volatility, stock crashes, compensation, labour market

1 Introduction

The labour market is always thriving if the stock market is overvalued, in this article the new setting is a kind of paradox, if there is a crash in stock market the labour market is

augmenting due to this loss just like when the broken window makes someone to come and fix it, it's a creator of a job: i have chosen the Asian option market because of its volatility and likelihood to compensate any loss in the stock market, we can also talk about how the labour market is getting up due to stock crashes and the reason is only expectations of investors about the recovery, this is also rational because of the history of trends which comes to emphasize on the choice of the fractional volatility for this course: people expect that before any downward trend the market was always high and they bet on the recovery pouring in funds in the company which use them to create jobs: my aim first of all is to emphasize on the classicals and how the laissez-faire holds in this model.

Frederic Bastiat in his treatie "*Ce qu'on voit et ce qu'on voit pas*" was arguing that employment and the labour market is getting importance in the fact a destruction hits the economy, Bastiat is not classical however he is a deft politician and polemist for whom i have esteem and preservation.

2 Model

When a crash or literally a loss in stock market occurs short rates are decreasing as a result of that depression: our vocation is to propose a model for such an equilibrium:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{t+1} &= S_t(1 - \lambda) + h_t \epsilon_t \\ r_{t+1} &= r_t(1 - \beta) + \epsilon_t \end{aligned}$$

Where $\lambda > 0$, $\beta > 0$, $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$, r is the short rate and S is the stock market price.

The Figarch model is specified as mean reverting equation using the following formula as a starting point:

$$\Phi(L)(1 - L)^d(\ln \sigma_t^2 - \omega) = \Psi(L)g(z_{t-1})$$

Where ω is the mean variance and $\Phi(L)$ and $\Psi(L)$ are polynomials in the lag operator, $\Phi(L) = (1 - \Phi_1 L) \times \dots (1 - \Phi_p L)$ and $\Psi(L) = (1 - \Psi_1 L) \times \dots (1 - \Psi_p L)$ and $(1 - L)^d$ is the fractional difference operator defined by its binomial expansion:

$$(1 - L)^d = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(i-d)}{\Gamma(-d)\Gamma(i+1)} L^i$$

The function g above is allowed to include the effect past returns has on the current volatility and has the following form:

$$g(z_t) = \theta z_t + \gamma(|z_t| - E|z_t|)$$

where $z_t = \frac{\epsilon_t}{\sigma_t}$ is the normalized innovation
we take into consideration the character volatility always shows as a mean reverting function tending to converge to a constant value and we should define it again as the following:

$$h_t = (1 - L)^d(\ln\sigma_t^2 - \omega)$$

It is then convenient to write the FIGARCH(1,d,1) model as:

$$h_t = (1 - L)^d(\ln\sigma_t^2 - \omega) = \Phi_1 h_{t-1} + g(z_{t-1}) + \Psi_1 g(z_{t-2})$$

3 Pricing of Asian Options under a rough volatility

Asian options are very volatile: we would be so euphoric in this section to allow ourselves: a way into modeling the market of Asian options to see afterward how there is a compensation between this market and the stock market: as Bastiat was arguing when there is a destruction somehow in an asset there is another job in the essence giving birth to a new industry thriving, how about stock market devaluation? The price of an Asian option with a strike K under absence of arbitrage is the following

$$A_t = E[\exp(-\int_t^T r_s ds) (\frac{1}{T-t+1} \int_t^T S_s ds - K)^+ / \mathcal{F}_t]$$

On the other hand

$$\begin{aligned} & E[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=t}^T S_i \mathbb{1}_{\sum_{i=t}^T S_i \geq nK} \exp(-\sum_{j=t}^T r_j) / \mathcal{F}_t] \\ &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=t}^T E[S_i \exp(-\sum_{j=t}^T r_j) \mathbb{1}_{\sum_{i=t}^T S_i \geq nK} / \mathcal{F}_t] \\ &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=t}^T (1 - \lambda)^m S_{i-m} E[\exp(-\sum_{j=t}^T r_j) \mathbb{1}_{\sum_{i=t}^T S_i \geq nK} / \mathcal{F}_t] \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand

$$\begin{aligned}
& E[\exp(-\sum_{j=t}^T r_j) \mathbb{1}_{\sum_{i=t}^T S_i \geq nK} / \mathcal{F}_t] \\
&= E[\exp(-\sum_{j=t}^T r_{j-1}(1-\beta) + \epsilon_j) \mathbb{1}_{\sum_{i=t}^T S_i \geq nK} / \mathcal{F}_t] \\
&= E[\exp(-\sum_{j=t}^T r_{j-m}(1-\beta)^m - \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} (1-\beta)^i \epsilon_{j-i}) \mathbb{1}_{\sum_{i=t}^T S_i \geq nK} / \mathcal{F}_t] \\
&= \exp(-\sum_{j=t}^T r_{j-m}(1-\beta)^m) \exp(\sum_{i=0}^{m-1} \frac{(1-\beta)^{2i}}{2}) P(\sum_{i=t}^T S_i \geq nK)
\end{aligned}$$

Where $T - m = t$

Vanilla options are easier to handle in pricing, we propose a pricing method for such a contract as the following, let's note the price of a european option C_t with strike price K .

$$C_t = E[\exp(-\int_t^T r_s ds) (S_T - K)^+ / \mathcal{F}_t]$$

On the other hand

$$\begin{aligned}
& E[S_T \exp(\sum_{j=t}^T r_j) \mathbb{1}_{S_T \geq K} / \mathcal{F}_t] \\
&= (1-\lambda)^n S_t E[\exp(-\sum_{j=t}^T r_{j-n}(1-\beta)^n + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (1-\beta)^i \epsilon_{j-i}) \mathbb{1}_{S_T \geq K} / \mathcal{F}_t] \\
&= (1-\lambda)^n S_t \exp(-\sum_{j=t}^T r_{j-n}(1-\beta)^n) \exp(\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \frac{(1-\beta)^{2i}}{2}) P(S_T \geq K)
\end{aligned}$$

4 Restrictions in the stock market crash under a rough volatility

The magnitude of the crash in the stock market is important to know which is the specific threshold in the downward trend that hits the stock market under our model to say that Asian options as a volatile market has the power to offset the loss in stock market, let's write the crash occuring in stock market as the following:

$$S_{t+1} = S_t - \lambda S_t j(t) + h_t \epsilon_t$$

Where $j(t) \in \{0, 1\}$

We would try to find out the optimal threshold of the crash that permits a compensation between stock market and Asian option market, as Frederic Bastiat had said, it's a beautiful analogy which states that the labour market won't get harmed by a loss in stock market, it would flourish instead if someone is willing to heal this downward trend, let's think of an investor that has pledged to invest in the suffering company if he bets on an upward trend after months or weeks, our vocation is to dictate a restriction for the following approach:

$$E[A_{t+1} - S_{t+1}/j(t) = 1] > 0$$

We would have the following restriction for the loss, λ which means the magnitude of the loss must be under a value to allow Asian option market to stabilize the stock market

$$\lambda < 1 - \frac{E[A_{t+1} + E[\frac{h_t^2}{2}]]}{E[S_t]}$$

Afterward we would assess the term $E[S_t]$ to see which is the threshold that we just talked about

$$E[S_t] = S_0 - \lambda E[j](S_t + S_{t-1} + \dots + S_{t-(m-1)})$$

We might assess the expected value of the Asian option under the risk neutral measure as the following:

$$E[A_{t+1}] = S_t + (\lambda + \gamma)S_t$$

Where γ is real positive shock that allows the market of Asian options to get above stock market expectations.

As Frederic Bastiat has said the economy is like a thriving industry that gets warmed upon the loss of a specific value, in this analogy i would be euphoric to lay down my thesis as the following:

$$E[L_{t+1}/\mathcal{F}_t] = L_t + A\lambda S_t$$

Where $A > 0$ and L is the number of the labour force which means that a shock in stock doesn't mean that real gdp is getting less of course, it's up to the reader to understand that any loss in stock market has to do with a liquidity from outside which can heal the broken share of stock, the broken window as in "*ce qu'on voit et ce qu'on voit pas*" book.

Hypothesis: Let's suppose the labour market moves in such an equilibrium:

$$L_{t+1} = L_t + \epsilon_t$$

Where $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$

On the other hand

$$\begin{aligned} L_t &= E[L_{t+1}/\mathcal{F}_t] \\ &= E[L_t + A\lambda S_t/\mathcal{F}_t] \\ &= L_t + A\lambda S_t \end{aligned}$$

Which means in other term that L is a martingale, we can't expect the movement of the labour market under the physical measure, we suppose that since investors not all of them have expectations about the recovery of the stock market in the case of a crash, they bet on an upward trend later on which could barely justify the existence of a probability H under which the labour market augments due to a crash in stock market.

Let's define this new equilibrium as the following

$$E^H[L_{t+1}/\mathcal{F}_t] = L_t + B\lambda S_t$$

Where $B > 0$

Which means the existence of a density function s defined as the following

$$\frac{dH}{dP} = s(t)$$

With the assumption that $E[s(t)/\mathcal{F}_t] = 1$ to exhibit the fact we are dealing with a density function

As L_t is a martingale under the physical measure we have the existence of depending time function $G(t)$ such that

$$L_{t+1} = L_t + G(t)\epsilon$$

With the **hypothesis** above that makes the labour market as a classical brownien motion under the physical measure, let's now look swiftly for the magnitude any loss in stock market affects the labour market, we have

$$\begin{aligned} L_t &= E^H[L_{t+1}/\mathcal{F}_t] \\ &= E^P[L_{t+1}s(t)/\mathcal{F}_t] \\ &= s(t)B(t) \end{aligned}$$

Which define the function s as the following

$$s_t = \frac{L_t + B\lambda S_t}{\sqrt{t}\epsilon}$$

Where $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$

We define *à priori* the density function s as the augmented new labour market per unit of time.

From the condition $E[s(t)/\mathcal{F}_t] = 1$ we find really the magnitude any stock crash could hit this stock share in question suffering badly from the loss, we have

$$B = \frac{\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sqrt{t}}{\exp(t^2)} dt - L_t}{\lambda S_t}$$

This argument is showing that we can believe that the fact investors expectations are willing to move against the market under such a probability universe when they would help the company in question to recover, it is all about expectations and the fact the market crash isn't riding everytime the economy into unemployment, the existence of such a universe of expectations is justified by some optimist investors that believe in the fact depressions in stock market don't lead to the worst, they bet on the opposition: while the market is reeling it's a rational argument about market efficiency theory and how the stock market efficiency is allowing markets to recover due to optimism and the existence of some rebel investors in some sense who are risk averse first of all because of their beliefs in the market in a whole.

The authors did not receive support from any organization for the submitted work. No funding was received to assist with the preparation of this manuscript. No funding was received for conducting this study. No funds, grants, or other support was received.

Ethical approval not applicable.

This article does not contain any studies with human participants performed by any of the authors.

All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

The datasets generated during and/or analysed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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